

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Paper

A Concise Review on Hyphenated Techniques: Liquid Chromatography Coupled Mass Spectroscopy (Lc-Ms/Ms)

S. J. Momin^{*1}, S. R. Shahi², L. P. Jain³, N. D. Kulkarni⁴, S. S. Gotpagar⁵, R. M. Savakhande⁶

^{1,3,4}Department of pharmaceutical chemistry Government College of Pharmacy Karad

^{2,5,6}Department of pharmaceuticals Government College of Pharmacy Karad

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 23 Feb. 2025

Keywords:

Hyphenated Techniques,
LC-MS, HPLC, MS,
Optimization, Resolution,
Ionization sources,
Detectors, bioanalytical
method, validation,
applications

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14913274

ABSTRACT

Hyphenated techniques combine spectroscopic and chromatographic methods like LC/MS for toxicology, drug monitoring, pharmacokinetic studies, and bioanalysis with interfaces like APCI and ESI for natural product analysis. Mass spectroscopy (MS) is an analytical technique used to determine the m/e ratio of charged analytes, calculate particle masses, and reveal chemical structures using ionization sources. HPLC and mass spectrometry coupling is complex due to high vacuum requirements, but interfaces like TSP, CFAB, API, and ESI overcome this, integrating detectors with liquid chromatographic separations. LC-MS is one of the hyphenated analytical methods that combine mass spectrometry and liquid chromatography for complex mixture analysis in biological, environmental, and pharmacological materials. It includes mobile phase reservoirs, pumps, degassers, auto samplers, columns, and detectors, with UV being the most common for stability and sensitivity. During the optimization stage, initial conditions such as resolution, peak shape, plate counts asymmetry, capacity factor, elution time, detection limits, limit of quantification, and overall analyte quantification ability are optimized. LC-MS/MS is a popular bioanalysis method for measuring medication concentrations in biological samples, making it the preferred quantitative analysis method between drug discovery and development. Validation of method by various parameters like accuracy precision etc. Applications of LC-MS in various fields like in structural elucidation.

INTRODUCTION

Pairing or combining two distinct analytical approaches with the aid of an appropriate interface

is known as a hyphenated technique. Spectroscopic techniques are mostly coupled with chromatographic techniques. Chromatography

***Corresponding Author:** S. J. Momin

Address: Department of pharmaceutical chemistry Government College of Pharmacy Karad

Email ✉: saniyamomin142@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

was used to separate the pure or almost pure fractions of chemical components in a mixture, while spectroscopy provides specific information that can be used to identify the components using standards or library spectra. The hyphenated technique is the result of integrating an internet-based spectroscopic detection technology with the separation approach. ^[1] Mass spectrometry/liquid chromatography, or LC/MS, is quickly taking the lead as the instrument preferred for liquid chromatographers. It is an excellent analytical method that combines mass spectrometry's detection specificity with liquid chromatography's resolving capability. ^[2] In laboratory medicine, it is still clear that LC-MS/MS is developing from the from the creative stage we discussed a decade ago to typical setups like automated analyser solutions that are frequently observed in contemporary laboratory conditions, it is still clear that LC-MS/MS in medical research is evolving. ^[3]

In conclusion, fundamental research findings that were used to the development of a method, piece of machinery, or measurement platform during a creative phase of technological development can occasionally be "forgotten" when they become commonplace. In this sense, immunoassays have changed from the research settings where they were initially developed and used. ^[4] In general, LC-MS is not widely used; less than 1% of studies conducted worldwide for MS-based laboratory diagnosis probably employ it. The relative numbers are significantly higher in specific application sectors, such toxicology and therapeutic drug monitoring (TDM), because there are fewer alternatives accessible. About 70% of organization taking part in proficiency testing employs LC-MS/MS for result creation when evaluating the immunosuppressive TDM. ^[5] It is an analytical method which fuses the physical separation abilities of liquid chromatography (often called HPLC) with the mass measuring powers of mass spectrometry. It is an analytical

approach that combines mass spectrometry's mass measurement abilities with liquid chromatography's (also known as HPLC) physical separation capabilities. LC-MS is a strong method employed in many applications because of its exceptional sensitivity and selectivity. It is frequently used in pharmacokinetic studies of medications and is the most popular technique in the field of bioanalysis. ^[6] Numerous LC-MS systems with a variety of interface choices are currently available on the market. Enough liquid nebulization and vaporization, sample ionization, solvent vapor removal, and ion extraction into the mass analyser are provided by the interface design. In the context of natural product analysis, atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI) and electrospray ionization (ESI) are the two most widely used interfaces. The latter is known as "the chromatographer's LC-MS interface" because of its high solvent flow rate capabilities, sensitivity, linear response, and versatility. These interfaces can be used with a variety of analyser types, such as quadrupole, ion trap, and TOF. Each of these analysers offers a different level of mass accuracy and resolution, though. The LC-UV-MS mode also allows for the utilization of continuous-flow FAB (LC-CF-FAB) and thermospray (LC-TSP-MS) interfaces. Because it allows an aqueous phase to enter the mass system at flow rate of 1-2 ml/min, which is commensurate with the flow rates commonly employed in phytochemical analysis, the TSP interface has been shown as being the ideal one for phytochemical analysis. ^[7]

Because the recently developed API-based methods cause moderate ionization, they can be used in conjunction with LC-tandem MS, which is enabled by a triple quadrupole system, or fragmentation-induced collisions in the interface itself for structure elucidation studies. Through the use of tandem mass spectrometry and stable isotope internal standards, it can be applied to biological molecules and, by optimizing the

technique to lessen the effects of ion repression, very sensitive and accurate procedures can be expanded. Between the drug development and discovery stages, technique validation is essential. Mass spectrometry and the physical separation of liquid chromatography, commonly referred to as HPLC, are combined in an analytical technique called LC-MS. A classic automated LC-MS system includes of an auto sampler, mass spectrometer, LC system, and double three-way diverter. The diverter usually acts as an automatic switching valve to send unwanted parts of the eluting from the LC system to trash before the sample enters the MS.^[8]

PRINCIPLE

Principles of Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS):

Analyte separation using interactions with the stationary phase and mobile phase is the foundation of liquid chromatography (LC). Different retention times are the result of analytes partitioning between phases.

Ionization of analytes into charged particles (ions) is the fundamental idea behind mass spectrometry (MS). Ions are separated according to the mass-to-charge ratio (m/z).

Interface between LC and MS:

1. Ionization via Electrospray (ESI)
2. Chemical Ionization at Atmospheric Pressure (APCI)
3. Photoionization of Atmospheric Pressure (APPI)

Workflow for LC-MS:

Fig1: Workflow For LC-MS

The basic principle of HPLC is surface adsorption. A sample is driven along a column containing a stationary phase in high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). This stationary phase is often composed of irregularly shaped or spherically formed particles that have been chosen or altered to accomplish specific kinds of separations. Octadecylsilyl (C18) and related organic modified particles serves as stationary

phase in RP using pH adjusted water organic mixture such as water-acetonitrile and water-methanol. In what are known as conventional phase liquid natural processes, materials such as colloid are used as stationary components with neat or mixed organic solutions.^[9, 10] One analytical technique for determining the m/e ratio of charged analyte is mass spectroscopy (MS). Particle masses may be calculated, the elemental

makeup of an analyte molecule can be determined, and the chemical structures of molecules, including peptides and other chemical compounds, can be revealed. The m/e ratios of charged molecules or molecular fragments produced by ionizing chemical substances are estimated using mass spectrometry.^[11] The interface between the mass spectrometer and the HPLC eluent can be any of a variety of ionization sources. The two most widely used sources are ESI and APCI, both of which are now commonplace parts of mass spectrometers used in LC-MS applications. Both APCI and ESI are commonly referred to as sources because the point of ionization for both is atmospheric pressure.^[12]

Coupling of Liquid Chromatography with Mass Spectrometry

When a liquid was introduced into a mass spectrometer's high vacuum at a flow rate of 1 milliliter per minute and then evaporated, the high vacuum would instantly break down, making the coupling of HPLC with mass spectrometry a highly delicate and complicated process for a long time. In order to get over this innate incompatibility, numerous interfaces were created, each with unique benefits and drawbacks.^[13]

We have not been able to obtain molecular ions for large nonvolatile molecules that are neutral in solution; however, ion-molecule reactions with reagent ions, either generated by gas-phase processes started by electron ionization or by thermospray from the buffer, can ionize molecules that are slightly volatile and thermally stable. In this operating mode, the system behaves remarkably similarly to the results of "desorption chemical ionization."^[14] With TSP, a heated capillary was used to deliver the eluent into the

vacuum, and a cold trap was used to extract the solvent vapor that was produced very challenging. For instance, the analyte was ionized by protonation using volatile additions such as ammonium acetate. The first interface designed to deal with thermolabile substances was TSP. The continuous-flow fast atom bombardment (CFFAB) interface was an additional interface.^[15] A small amount, roughly 5 ml/min, was divided into the mass spectrometer after a matrix with low volatility, like glycerol, was introduced to the HPLC eluent (2–5%). The dissolved analytes were left behind in a thin layer of glycerol after the solvent had evaporated from, say, a metal frit. The analytes were desorbed from this film by being bombarded with caesium ions or energetic xenon atoms. Although CFFAB was a rather sensitive technique, it was challenging to keep the glycerol film renewing steadily and maintaining a nice peak shape. Because the particle beam (PB) interface provides typical EI spectra that can be found in commercially available libraries, it is still rather significant.^[16] About ten years ago, the so-called atmospheric pressure ionization (API) interfaces were introduced, and HPLC/MS became a success story. The HPLC eluent is evaporated outside the mass spectrometer via API interfaces. In order to eliminate the need to pump off massive amounts of gas, the analyte is also ionized outside the spectrometer at atmospheric pressure. Only the ions produced are then put into the mass spectrometer. Consequently, it is now simple to integrate mass spectrometric detectors with liquid chromatographic separations. Electrospray ionization (ESI) is the most popular interface technique, and APCI comes in second.^[17, 18]

INSRUMENTATION

Fig 2: Instrumentation of LC-MS

LC-MS is a powerful analytical technique that combines the separation capabilities of liquid chromatography (LC) with the identification and quantification abilities of mass spectrometry (MS). This synergistic combination enables the analysis of complicated mixtures, such as those found in biological, environmental, and pharmaceutical components.

Crucial Components of an LC-MS System:

- 1) Mobile phase reservoirs: How Mobile Phase Reservoirs Are Used in High Performance Liquid Chromatography. The pump will push the mobile phase solution into the column after it has been transported by the mobile phase reservoir. This movement is caused by the gravitational pull. When employed as mobile phase in LC, the solvents and solutions are stored in solvent reservoirs. These reservoirs are basically feed-receiving glass bottles or flasks
- 2) Pump: Provides a steady flow rate of the solvent mixture, or mobile phase.

Three typical pump types

1. Pumps with constant pressure: Because of a constant pressure, they, as their name implies, produce a constant flow rate in column. The low pressure of a gas inside a cylinder is used to generate the high pressure of the mobile phase that is required.
2. Syringe type pumps:
3. Reciprocating piston pumps:

- 3) Mixer
- 4) Degasser: Four methods used for degassing in HPLC are:
 1. Sonication
 2. Vacuum
 3. Helium sparging
 4. In-line degassing.
- 5) Autosampler: Injects samples into the LC system automatically.
- 6) Column: Divides the sample's constituent parts according to how they interact with stationary phase. Normal phase, reverse phase, ion exchange, and size exclusion columns are the four primary varieties of HPLC columns. Every form of column is appropriate for a variety of applications and has pros and cons of its own.

The primary use of size exclusion HPLC columns is in the separation of proteins and carbohydrates. Racemic mixtures can be resolved using a chiral HPLC column; additional HPLC column types include displacement, affinity, and ion exclusion chromatography columns.

- 7) Detector: Due to its high sensitivity, ease of use, and superior durability, the ultraviolet (UV) or visible (VIS) detector is the most often used in HPLC (1). There are three major types of UV/VIS detectors are diode array detectors, fixed wavelength detectors, and variable wavelength detectors

Other

1. Fluorescence
 2. Refractive index
 3. Conductivity
 4. Flame ionization detector
- ❖ Interface

Ionization Source: Converts the analytes from the liquid phase to gas-phase ions. Common ionization techniques include:

1. **Electrospray ionization (ESI):** Soft ionization technique suitable for polar and ionic compounds.
2. **Atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI):** Soft ionization technique suitable for less polar compounds.
3. **Matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization (MALDI):** Hard ionization technique suitable for large biomolecules.

Mass instrumentation

- 1) **Vaporization chamber:** Simply said, a mass spectrometer is made up of an input chamber

Fig 3: Ionization techniques

- 3) **Ion acceleration chamber:** Any ion with the exact same kinetic energy is driven with an electric field into the "field-free" drift zone, which is devoid of electrical fields. An electric field is used to accelerate ions farther from the ion source.
- 4) **Mass Analyzer:** uses the m/z ratio of the ions to separate them. Typical mass analyzers consist of:
 1. **Quadruple:** a straightforward and reliable tool for monitoring specific ions.
 2. **Triple Quadrupole:** Used for quantitative analysis, this tool is extremely sensitive and selective.

that is used to inject and evaporate the substance to be studied. All of its parts function under a high vacuum. After entering an ionization chamber, the gaseous molecules are subjected to a high-energy electron beam. Among other things, the electron beam produces a molecular ion, which is a positively charged molecule, created when one electron is removed from the molecule. After then, the molecule ion may fragment into smaller pieces. The pieces that are positively charged

- 2) **Chamber of ionization:** In mass spectrometry, a variety of ionization techniques are employed. Fast Atom Bombardment (FAB) and electron impact (EI) are the traditional techniques that the majority of chemists are familiar with.

Ionization Technique

3. **Time-of-Flight (TOF):** Used for precise mass measurements, it has a high mass accuracy and resolution.
4. **Ion Trap:** Used for qualitative as well as quantitative investigation, this tool has high sensitivity and adaptability.
5. **Fourier Transform Ion Cyclotron Resonance (FT-ICR):** Ultra-high mass accuracy and resolution, used for complex mixture analysis.
- 5) **Detector:** Detects the separated ions and generates a mass spectrum.

Some of the commonly used types include

1. Electron multipliers (EM)
2. Faraday cups (FC)
3. Photomultiplier conversion dynodes

4. Array detectors.

OPTIMIZATION OF LC-MS METHOD

Resolution and peak shape, plate counts asymmetry, capacity factor, elution time, detection limits, limit of quantification, and overall ability to

quantify the particular analyte of interest are among the initial sets of conditions that have developed from the first stages of development and are enhanced or maximized during the optimization stage. When developing a method, the following parameters need to be optimized:

Fig 4: Optimization parameters

A. Selection of mode of separation: The main determinant of the mode of separation is the analyte's nature. Reverse phase is the most favored mode for the separation of polar or moderately polar substances. The mobile phase seems significantly polar in nature than the stationary phase while in reverse phase mode. Electrospray ionization (ESI) was used for detection; a triple quadrupole mass spectrometer with an ESI interface allowed for both positive and negative ionization modes of operation. MS/MS detection is provided by the selective reaction monitoring mode (SRM/MRM). Techniques for gathering and displaying LC/MS data the mass spectrometer are usually configured to scan a particular mass range. This mass scan could be relatively narrow, as in selective ion monitoring, or it can be extensive, as in complete scan analysis. The following are the most common ways to obtain LC/MS data:

- 1) The standard total ion current plot (TIC) is produced by full scanning acquisition.
- 2) SIM, or selected ion monitoring.
- 3) Monitoring numerous reactions (MRM) or selected reactions (SRM).

B. Selection of column: The column is the central component of the chromatographic apparatus.

High separation capability of column material (micro particles, 5-10 μm in size) packed to allow for the maximum number of theoretical plates. The most common ingredient used in the production of packing materials is silica (SiO_2 , H_2O). It is composed of an upright, three-dimensional network of siloxane links (Si-O-Si) with interconnecting pores. As a result, a large variety of commercial items are accessible, with particle sizes ranging from 3 to 50 μm and surface areas between 100 and 800 m^2/g . Silica's polarity is attributed to its silanol groups, which are used in adsorption chromatography with non-polar organic eluents. Although materials with C4 and C8 chains are also available, octadecyl-silica (ODS-Silica), which has C18 chains, the most widely used.

C. Mobile phase selection: Selectivity in LC is typically changed by altering the stationary phase's functionality or the composition of the mobile phase. Optimizing the composition of the mobile phase by varying the solvent type and strength, buffer type and concentration, and pH has proven to be the most effective and practical solution in the short term, especially for the study of ion compounds. The most often used solvents in LC/ESI-MS are

acetonitrile admixtures, water, isopropanol, and methanol.^[20]

Optimization of Mass Spectrometric Parameters

- ✓ Ionization Source: Ion formation and detection efficiency are affected by the ionization source selection (e.g., electrospray ionization, atmospheric pressure chemical ionization). It ought to be customized to the APS's physicochemical characteristics.
- ✓ Enhancing the specificity and sensitivity of the approach is possible by optimizing collision energy and mass transitions. To select the target analyte ions and increase signal-to-noise ratios, collision-induced dissociation (CID)

and selective reaction monitoring (SRM) are frequently employed.^[21]

Introduction to Bioanalytical Method Developmen

Medication concentrations in biological samples are precisely measured thanks to bioanalysis, which is essential to medication development. Due to its advantages over conventional techniques, including increased sensitivity and specificity, LC-MS/MS has become more and more popular in recent years. The assessment and interpretation of bioavailability, bioequivalence, and pharmacokinetic data are made easier by the use of bioanalytical techniques for the quantitative determination of medications and their metabolites in biological matrix.^[22]

Fig 5: Biological matrix

Between drug discovery and development, quantitative analysis of medications and their metabolites in biological fluids is essential. For that, LC-MS is the recommended methodology.

The following procedures are used to construct the LC-MS method:^[23]

Fig 6: Construction the LC-MS method

Validation of Bioanalytical Methods ^[24]

Fig 7: Validation parameters

a. Accuracy:

Method Comparison: Examine the outcomes of the bioanalytical approach in comparison to a reference or accepted methodology. To evaluate agreement, use statistical techniques such as Bland-Altman plots or regression analysis.

Studies that are spiking: Compare the measured concentrations with the anticipated concentrations after adding known quantities of the analyte to the matrix (spiked samples). Analyze matrix effects and recovery during the spiking studies.

b. Precision:

Intra-day Precision: Examine several duplicates of the same sample in the same day under identical circumstances. Determine the results' standard deviation (SD) or relative standard deviation (RSD).

Analyze duplicates of the exact same sample on various days or by various analyzers to determine intermediate precision, also known as inter-day precision. Add variances like various analysts, instruments, and days. Compute the results' SD or RSD.

c. Sensitivity

In bioanalysis, sensitivity is the analytical method's capacity to precisely identify and measure analyte concentrations at low levels. Sensitivity is essential for identifying traces of active pharmaceutical substances (APS) in

biological matrices in the context of bioanalysis, especially when working with pharmaceuticals.

d. Selectivity

The ability of an analytical technique to precisely quantify the analyte being studied in its presence of additional components is known as selectivity in bioanalysis. Selectivity reduces false positives or negatives and guarantees that the method's reaction is unique to the target analyte.

e. Linearity

The potential of an analytical technique to give finding that are exactly proportionate to the concentration of analyte in the material being tested throughout a specific range is known as linearity. This implies that in bioanalysis, there should be a linear relationship among the concentration of analyte and the instrument response.

f. Range

The difference between the lowest and maximum analyte concentrations that have been shown to be reliably quantified with respectable precision and accuracy is known as the analytical method's range. It is a crucial parameter that establishes whether the procedure can be applied to particular concentration levels.

APPLICATIONS OF LC-MS/MS

Information like compound resolution, identity, and quantification can be obtained via LC-MS. Additionally; it facilitates chemical separation and purification. Other uses for LC-MS include.

Table no 1: Applications of LC-MS/MS.

Sr. No.	Application	Recent use	Reference
1	Molecular Pharmacognosy	Utilized for the research of ingredient differences in phenotypic cloning studies as well as in the contents and classifications of various groupings of cultivated plant cells.	25
2	Molecular weight determination	Able to determine the molecule weight of chemical substance, pharmaceutical substances, proteins, etc.	26
3	Structural determination/elu- cidation	Tandem mass spectrometry used to determine structural information using mass spectral fragmentations.	26
4	Pharmaceutical applications	It's used to determine the pharmacokinetic profile of the pharmaceuticals like drug, drug metabolites/degradation product, impurities and chiral impurities.	27
5	Proteomics	In proteomics investigations for drug development, which include target protein characterization and biomarker discovery, liquid chromatography/mass spectrometry has emerged as a potent method.	28
6	Automated Immunoassay in Therapeutic Drug Monitoring	Liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) methods and immunoassays appear to be the most widely used approaches in clinical laboratories today. TDM of certain drugs with a narrow therapeutic index aids in the improvement of patient outcomes.	29
7	Two Dimensional (2-D) Hyphenated Technology	(2D) hyphenated technology for use in the primary classification in the domains of genomics, lipidomics, metabolomics, proteomics, and so forth, as well as in a variety of analytical and bioanalytical techniques for the analysis of proteins, amino acids, nucleic acids, amino acids, carbohydrates, lipids, peptides, and so forth.	30
8	Clinical chemistry and toxicology	The analytes that are evaluated include oestradiol, testosterone, thyroid hormones, immunosuppressants, vitamin D, steroids for newborn screening programs, and clinical and forensic toxicology. Despite the fact that immunoassays are frequently employed in clinical laboratories, many of the analytes examined in standard clinical laboratories have low analytical sensitivity and specificity.	31
9	Food and Environmental applications	Use to measure the amount of vitamin D3 in chicken feed additives, identify aflatoxins (toxic metabolic products in some fungi), etc.	32
10	LC-MS/MS in drug metabolism & toxicology studies	Three main categories can be used to categorize research on the metabolic fate of drugs in living systems: mechanistic studies to identify chemically reactive metabolites, quantitative studies to determine the pharmacokinetic of parent drug or its primary metabolites, as well as qualitative studies to clarify metabolic pathways.	33

11	LC-MS/MS as quantification method for biogenic amines	Amines that contain biogenic substrates, such as catecholamines, serotonin, and histamine, are referred to as biogenic amines. It makes it possible to routinely quantify biomarkers in low concentration ranges and to assess biogenic amines and metabolites with greater sensitivity and specificity.	34
----	---	--	----

REFERENCES

- Chinchole R, Hatre P M, ujwala Chavan R. Recent applications of hyphenated liquid chromatography techniques in forensic toxicology: A review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences Review and Research*. 2012; 14:57–63.
- Sharma B K. *Instrumental methods of chemical analysis*. Krishna Prakashan Media; 1981.
- Armbruster D A, Overcash DR, Reyes J. Clinical Chemistry Laboratory Automation in the 21st Century - Amat Victoria curam (Victory loves careful preparation). *Clin Biochem Rev*. 2014;35(3):143–53.
- Wu AHB, French D. Implementation of liquid chromatography/mass spectrometry into the clinical laboratory. *Clin Chim Acta*. 2013; 420:4–10. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cca.2012.10.026>
- Seger C, Shipkova M, Christians U, Billaud EM, Wang P, Holt DW, et al. Assuring the proper analytical performance of measurement procedures for immunosuppressive drug concentrations in clinical practice: Recommendations of the International Association of Therapeutic Drug Monitoring and Clinical Toxicology immunosuppressive drug scientific committee. 2016 Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/FTD.0000000000000269>
- Beckett A H, Stenlake GH. *Practical Pharmaceutical Chemistry*. CBS.
- Wolfender J L, Hostettmann K, Abe F, Nagao T, Okabe H, Yamauchi T. Liquid chromatography combined with thermospray and continuous-flow fast atom bombardment mass spectrometry of glycosides in crude plant extracts. *J Chromatogr A* 1995;712(1):155–68. Available from: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0021-9673\(95\)00522-o](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/0021-9673(95)00522-o)
- English J W, editor. *Pharmaceutical analysis Part A: modern methods*.
- Arpino P. Combined liquid chromatography mass spectrometry. Part I. Coupling by means of a moving belt interface. *Mass Spectrom Rev*. 1989;8(1):35–55. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/mas.1280080103>
- Caprioli R M. Continuous-flow fast atom bombardment mass spectrometry. *Anal Chem*. 1990;62(8):477A-485A. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/ac00207a715>
- Beckett A H, Stenlake GH. *Practical Pharmaceutical Chemistry*. CBS.
- Niessen W M A. Progress in liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry instrumentation and its impact on high-throughput screening. *J Chromatogr A*. 2003;1000(1–2):413–36. Available from: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0021-9673\(03\)00506-5](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0021-9673(03)00506-5)
- Games D E, Hirter P, Kuhn W, Lewis E, Weerasinghe NCA, Westwood SA. Studies of combined liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry with a moving-belt interface. *J Chromatogr A*. 1981; 203:131–8. Available from: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0021-9673\(00\)80287-3](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0021-9673(00)80287-3)
- Blakley C R, Vestal M L. Thermospray interface for liquid chromatography-mass

- spectrometry. *Analytical Chemistry*. 1983; 55:750–4.
15. Caprioli R M. Continuous-flow fast atom bombardment mass spectrometry. *Anal Chem* . 1990;62(8):477A-485A. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/ac00207a715>
 16. Willoughby R C, Browner RF. Monodisperse aerosol generation interface for combining liquid chromatography with mass spectroscopy. *Anal Chem*. 1984;56(14):2626–31. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/ac00278a003>
 17. The Principle, Types, and Applications of Mass Spectrometry: A Comprehensive Review Sabitha Vadakedath1*, Venkataramana Kandi1, Vikram Godishala2, Venkata Bharat Kumar Pinnelli3. (n.d.).
 18. Whitehouse C M, Dreyer R N, Yamashita M, Fenn JB. Electrospray interface for liquid chromatographs and mass spectrometers. *Anal Chem*. 1985;57(3):675–9. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/ac00280a023>
 19. Willard H H, Merritt L L, Jr J A, Dean F A. Jr, *Instrumental methods of Analysis*, CBS Publishers and distributors pvt.
 20. Bhole R P, Jagtap S R, Chadar K B, Zambare Y B. Liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry technique-A review. *Res J Pharm Technol* . 2020;13(1):505. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5958/0974-360x.2020.00097.9>
 21. Shreyash N, Vaibhav S. Bioanalytical Method Development and Validation for Estimation of Active Pharmaceutical Substance by LC-MS/MS: A General Review on Bioanalysis. *Bioanalysis International Journal Of Research And Analytical Reviews*. 2024; 11:69–81
 22. Bressolle F, Bromet-Petit M, Audran M. Validation of liquid chromatographic and gas chromatographic methods. Applications to pharmacokinetics. *J Chromatogr B Biomed Appl*. 1996;686(1):3–10. Available from: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0378-4347\(96\)00088-6](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s0378-4347(96)00088-6)
 23. Bhole R P, Jagtap S R, Chadar K B, Zambare Y B. Liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry technique-A review. *Res J Pharm Technol*. 2020;13(1):505. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5958/0974-360x.2020.00097.9>
 24. Shreyash N, Vaibhav S. Bioanalytical Method Development and Validation for Estimation of Active Pharmaceutical Substance by LC-MS/MS: A General Review on Bioanalysis. *Bioanalysis International Journal of Research And Analytical Reviews*. 2024; 11:69–81
 25. Seger C, Shipkova M, Christians U, Billaud EM, Wang P, Holt DW, et al. Assuring the proper analytical performance of measurement procedures for immunosuppressive drug concentrations in clinical practice: Recommendations of the International Association of Therapeutic Drug Monitoring and Clinical Toxicology immunosuppressive drug scientific committee. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1097/FTD.0000000000000269>
 26. Kavitha P N, Mrs P. Instrumental methods of analysis.
 27. Kang J-S. Principles and applications of LC-MS/MS for the quantitative bioanalysis of analytes in various biological samples. In: *Tandem Mass Spectrometry - Applications and Principles*. InTech; 2012.
 28. Brandhorst G, Oellerich M, Maine G, Taylor P, Veen G, Wallemacq P. Liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry or automated immunoassays: what are the future trends in therapeutic drug monitoring *Clin Chem*. 2012;58(5):821–5 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1373/clinchem.2011.167189>
 29. Wu A H B, French D. Implementation of liquid chromatography/mass spectrometry into the

- clinical laboratory. *Clin Chim Acta.* 2013; 420:4–10. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cca.2012.10.026>
30. Steiner W E. Emerging trends in liquid chromatography and mass spectrometry instrumentation for analytical & bioanalytical techniques. *J Anal Bioanal Tech.* 2012;03(04). Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.4172/2155-9872.1000e106>
31. Thomson B A. Atmospheric pressure ionization and liquid chromatography/mass spectrometry—together at last. *J Am Soc Mass Spectrom.* 1998;9(3):187–93. Available from: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s1044-0305\(97\)00285-7](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s1044-0305(97)00285-7)
32. Kaufmann B, Souverain S, Cherkaoui S, Christen P, Veuthey J-L. Rapid liquid chromatographic-mass spectrometric analysis of withanolides in crude plant extracts by use of a monolithic column. *Chromatographia.* 2002;56(3–4):137–41. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/bf02493201>
33. Arpino P, Baldwin M A, McLafferty F W. Liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry. II. Continuous monitoring. *Biomed Mass Spectrom.* 1974;1(1):80–2. Available from: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/bms.1200010117>
34. Thomson B A. Atmospheric pressure ionization and liquid chromatography/mass spectrometry—together at last. *J Am Soc Mass Spectrom.* 1998;9(3):187–93. Available from: [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s1044-0305\(97\)00285-7](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/s1044-0305(97)00285-7).

HOW TO CITE: S. J. Momin*, S. R. Shahi, L. P. Jain, N. D. Kulkarni, S. S. Gotpagar, R. M. Savakhande, A Concise Review on Hyphenated Techniques: Liquid Chromatography Coupled Mass Spectroscopy (Lc-Ms/Ms), *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 2, 1856-1868. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14913274>